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Influence of Recycling and Healing on Flow Number (FN) of Reclaimed Asphalt Pavement (RAP)

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ABSTRACT

Healing the microcracks of AC mixture is a sustainable property which prolongs the useful life of the AC pavement. Recycling of aged flexible pavement is a sustainable process used to extend the life of the pavement. In the present work, Reclaimed Asphalt Pavement (RAP) was obtained from the in-service field pavement and recycled with a mixture of binder and carbon black. Laboratory specimens of Marshall size were prepared from both recycled and the control RAP mixtures and tested under dynamic indirect tensile stress (DITS) and dynamic double punching shear stresses (DDPSS) at moderate temperature of 20°C. A constant stress level of 138 kPa was implemented. The testing was conducted in the pneumatic repeated load system PRLS with constant loading frequency of 60 cycles per minute. The dynamic loading sequence for each cycle is 0.1 seconds of load duration and 0.9 seconds of rest period. The test was terminated after 1200 cycles of dynamic stress which allowed for the initiation of micro cracks. Specimens were stored in an oven for 120 min at 60 °C to allow for crack healing by external heating technique. The healed specimens were subjected to another round of DITS and DDPSS and the variations in the permanent microstrain (PM) and FN were recorded. It was observed that the FN declined by 212 % after recycling and declined by 44.4 % after healing when tested by DITS. PM increased by 14.2 after recycling while it declined by 166 % at failure for both aged and recycled mixtures after healing. However, FN of AC mixture declined by 18.2 % and declined by 66.6 % after healing. PM increased by (100, and 340) % for recycled and after healing under DDPSS cycles respectively. The recycling index before healing is lower by 50 % for DITS test as compared with that at DDPSS test. However, the recycling index after healing is lower by 30 % for DITS test as compared with that at DDPSS test. On the other hand, the healing index at failure showed no significant variation among the testing mode. FN is

recommended as a sound measure for the efficiency of recycling process.

Keywords: *Microstrain, flow number, healing, recycling, asphalt concrete, dynamic, tensile, shear*

INTRODUCTION

Xiao et al., [1] used the shear modulus and volume of AC mixture after practicing the healing process as evaluation indexes for the self-healing ability of AC by dynamic shear test. The results show that the free volume increases while the cohesive energy density of AC declines. The shear and bulk modulus declines, and the self-healing property of AC decreases. When the AC mixture transitions from a high-temperature to a low-temperature state, its influence in the low-temperature state is significant on the healing performance of AC. Self-healing mechanism of recycled, virgin, and aged asphalt was assessed by Yu, et al., [2] in different environments. The self-healing process was analyzed and correlated with parameters. The test results showed that rapid reorganization of molecules around cracks initiates and the formation of self-healing networks occurs. The study clarifies the role of thermal self-healing mechanism of asphalt cracks at multiple scales, ensuring the sustainable use of AC. Miljković et al., [3] evaluated the healing and damage characteristics of AC mixture. Samples of reclaimed asphalt by a recycling agent were prepared. The damage was characterized using dynamic shear cyclic stresses while the healing response was assessed after rest periods. The mechanical analysis was conducted by correlating results before and after applying rest periods and dynamic loading. The mechanical analysis demonstrated that using recycling agent or higher binder content improved its healing capability. High benhancesontent formed spherical pores which enhances the strength of AC mixture, while low binder content developed elongated interconnected pores which coalesced into microcracks and increase damage susceptibility while

reducing the healing potential. Asadi and Tabatabaee, [4] stated that asphalt binder is known to exhibit an inherent ability to repair interior damage named (self-healing potentially) which affects the performance in fatigue damage of AC mixture. Their study defined three healing indices to quantify the healing potential of asphalt binders using damage characteristic curves. Initial, residual, and total healing indices described the changes in the accumulated damage after the rest period and the lasting effect of healing. The testing results demonstrated the detrimental influence of ageing, and the positive impact of the use of the rejuvenator agent. Healing models were developed. He et al., [5] simulated the self-healing process of AC mixed with a healing agent, atomic and plant oil were used as healing agent for AC mixture. Test results showed that the healing rate of aged AC can be improved by aromatic oil. However, the healing rate of virgin AC can be improved by plant oil. The healing agent was better effective at high temperature. Sarsam, [6] assessed the impact of healing of AC mixture on the deformation parameters under the action of dynamic compressive and flexural stresses. It was concluded that the deformation declined by (84.2 and 28.6) % when tested by dynamic flexural and dynamic compressive stresses respectively after healing. Preethi Shylaja and Ravichandran, [7] investigated the physical properties and rutting behavior of recycled AC developed with Nano clay and Nano silica. The test results indicate that modifying the binder with nanomaterials has reduced moisture damage, reported higher tensile strength ratio, showed better performance in terms of durability and strength and enhanced the rutting potential of the recycled AC

mixtures. Sarsam and Mahdi, [8] investigated the influence of recycling of aged AC mixture with SBR and carbon black. Specimens were prepared and tested for crack healing, DITS and dynamic compressive stress. The influence of crack healing was identified in terms of the change in permanent deformation and Resilient Modulus for each recycling agent. It was concluded that the resilient modulus increases after healing while the permanent deformation declined after healing. Preethi and Ravichandran, [9] developed recycled AC mixes of RAP and modified asphalt binder with nanomaterials. Waste cooking oil was used as a rejuvenator. It was found that implementation of nanomaterial has improved the strength of AC mixtures. The test result revealed that recycled AC mixtures exhibit higher indirect tensile strength, and higher resistance to dynamic stability and rutting as compared with control mixes. Mullapudi et al., [10] assessed the healing and fatigue characteristics of RAP mixtures with various healing periods between loads. The fatigue lives and healing of different RAP mixes were evaluated. The degree of healing was found to depend on rest period and RAP content. Different aging indexes of the binders and Surface free energy showed good correlation with the healing index of the AC mixes. It was concluded that such correlation is expected to improve the understanding of the healing and fatigue behavior of RAP mixes. Liu et al., [11] developed an enhanced method which may eliminate the dependence to calculate FN on the termination strain. The results exhibited that there is a unique relationship between strain rate and FN during the secondary stage, which is independent of AC type, test temperature, and stress level. Faccin et al., [12] evaluated the rutting of different AC mixtures using uniaxial dynamic load test in a criteria proposal for the parameter FN depending on traffic. The results showed

that the modification of the binder was the most influential characteristics in the rutting initiation of AC. A new criterion was suggested. Yu et al., [13] investigated the microscopic and macroscopic changes of physical property of multiple recycling AC through laboratory tests. The results indicate that after multiple recycling, the solubility of rejuvenator in old AC decreases exponentially with the increasing number of recycling cycles. It was concluded that the high temperature stability of recycled AC mixtures gradually increases with the number of recycling cycles, and the Marshall volumetric properties of the recycled AC mixtures can meet the regulatory requirement. However, the low-temperature cracking resistance performance of the recycled AC mixtures deteriorates rapidly. Zhang et al., [14] compared dynamic modulus, FN, and uniaxial dynamic load deformation tests usually used to characterize AC mixes for rutting resistance potential. Laboratory test results showed that the FN Index can correlate well with results of both the dynamic modulus and dynamic uniaxial stress tests.

The aim of the present assessment is to assess the suitability of implementing the FN in evaluating the efficiency of recycling process and suitability of (asphalt binder + carbon black) rejuvenator for enhancing the quality of RAP and controlling the deformation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Rap Material

The RAP mixture was obtained from the demolished AC from binder course layer of highway section at Karbala province. Table 1 exhibits its properties as per ASTM, [15] requirements, while Figure 1 shows the gradation of aggregates. It can be noticed that the gradation of RAP mixture is still within the required specification limits of AC binder course according to SCRB, [16] requirements.

The recycling rejuvenator was prepared in the laboratory; various percentages of carbon black were tried (0.5 to 3) % with 0.5 % increments. Asphalt cement was heated to 110 °C, and the carbon black was added gradually to the asphalt cement and mixed thoroughly until homogenous blend was obtained. Mixtures were tested for consistency, and the obtained optimum

carbon black content was 1.5 % by weight of the binder. More details of the preparation process could be found in Sarsam and Mahdi, [17]. Table 3 exhibits the physical properties of the Rejuvenator. Table 4 presents the rheological properties of the rejuvenator.

Table 3: Physical Properties of Asphalt Cement and Rejuvenator.

Property Value	Test Conditions	ASTM, [15] Designation No.	Asphalt cement	Rejuvenator (binder+1.5 % Carbon black)
Penetration	25°C, 100gm, 5sec	D5-06	43	38
Softening Point	-	D36-95	46	50
Ductility	25°C, 5cm/min	D113-99	140	132
Flash Point	Cleave land open cup	D92-05	269	218
After Thin Film Oven Test D1754-97				
Retained Penetration of Residue (%)	25°C, 100gm, 5sec	D5-06	57	51
Ductility of Residue	25°C, 5cm/min	D113-99	73	62
Loss on Weight	163° C, 50 gm, 5 hours	-	0.23	0.27

Table 4: Rheological properties of asphalt cement and Rejuvenator.

Property Value	AC (40-50)	Rejuvenator (binder + 1.5 % Carbon black)
Penetration Index (PI)	- 2.54	- 1.77
Temperature of Equivalent Stiffness (TES), (°C)	- 6	- 9
Viscosity Temperature Susceptibility (VTS), (centipoises/kelvin)	0.1494	0.1024
Penetration Viscosity Number (PVN),	- 1.0862	- 1.095
Stiffness modulus (N/m ²)	1.5 * 10 ⁹	1.2 * 10 ⁹

Preparation of AC Specimens

The control RAP was heated to 150° C, and various doses of the rejuvenator were tried (1 to 4) % with 1% increment. The optimum dose of the rejuvenator was 2 % by weight of the existing binder in the RAP based on testing of trial Marshall specimens for Volumetric properties and

Marshall Stability and flow. More details on such trials and preparation of specimens may be referred to Mahdi and Sarsam, [18]. Table 5 exhibits the Marshall properties of RAP and Rejuvenated AC mixtures. A total of 24 Marshall specimens were prepared for the dynamic testing process of DITS and DDPSS using 75

blows of Marshall hammer on each face of the specimen. It can be noticed that more

flexible mixture was obtained after implementation of rejuvenator.

Table 5: Marshall and Volumetric properties of RAP and Rejuvenated AC mixtures.

Properties	RAP	RAP + 2 % Rejuvenator
Asphalt content (%)	3.84	3.92
Stability (kN)	17.5	9.6
flow (mm)	2.9	3.08
Bulk density	2.320	2.324
Air voids (%)	5.1	4.4

Testing for DITS and DDPSS

Part of the prepared AC specimens (control and recycled) were subjected to DITS at 20° C environment with the aid of the Pneumatic Repeated Load System (PRLS). Specimens were tested at constant stress level of 138 kPa. The constant loading frequency was 60 cycles per minute. The

dynamic loading sequence for each cycle is 0.1 seconds of stress duration and 0.9 seconds of rest period. The test was terminated after 1200 cycles of dynamic stress which allowed for the initiation of micro cracks. Figure 2 demonstrates the PRLS testing chamber and the dynamic testing setup.

Fig. 2: Dynamic testing setup.

Healing Process of Microcracks

AC specimens which have been withdrawn from the PRLS chamber, were stored in an oven for 120 minutes at 60°C to allow for the microcrack healing process by external heating. After that, the specimens were put back in the PRLS chamber, conditioned for 60 minutes at 20 ±1°C, and then put through another set of dynamic stressors. AC specimens were tested in triplicate, and the average PM and FN of three specimens were considered for analysis as recommended by Sarsam, [19]. Data was

analyzed, and the plot of microstrain-load repetitions was conducted before and after microcrack healing process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Variation of FN at DITS Cycles

Figure 3 demonstrates the variation in FN of AC after recycling and crack healing when practicing (DITS). The control AC mixture (before healing) exhibits sharp increase in PM as the dynamic stress proceeds. The recycled mixture exhibited

higher PM when compared with that of the aged mixture. This could be attributed to the fact that the aged mixture is stiffer than the recycled mixture due to the loss in volatiles content during the ageing process. The cohesion of the mixture increases and the adhesion of the asphalt binder with aggregate gets harder. The susceptibility of the aged AC mixture to deformation due to loading declines after ageing and the FN is higher than that of the recycled AC mixture. However, after recycling the aged AC mixture, the PM increases due to the added flexibility by the recycling agent (asphalt binder + carbon black). High surface area of carbon black and high adsorption intensify the adhesive property of the aged AC. Figure 3-A shows that the PM increases by 200 % after the first cycle of DITS while it is higher than that of aged mixture by 14.2 % at failure. On the other hand, the FN declined by 212 % after recycling. When the AC mixture was

subjected to microcrack healing process, the PM declined by 166 % at failure for both aged and recycled mixtures while it declined by 33.3 % for recycled mixture after the first cycle of DITS as demonstrated in Figure 3-B. This behavior may be attributed to the regaining structural strength of AC mixture after the healing process. However, the FN of aged AC mixture after healing increased by 66.6 % as compared with that of aged mixture before healing. After the healing process, the FN of recycled AC mixture declined by 90 % as compared with that of aged mixture. The FN of recycled AC mixture after healing declined by 44.4 % when compared with FN of recycled mixture before the healing process. It can be revealed that the recycling agent had enhanced the healing potential of AC mixture and improved its resilience and flexibility. Similar findings were reported by Xiao et al., [1].

Fig. 3: Influence of healing and recycling on the FN at DITS.

Variation of FN at DDPSS Cycles

Figure 4 exhibits the variation in FN due to microcrack healing and recycling of the aged AC mixture when the test was conducted and the AC specimens practiced the DDPSS. For the control AC mixture, Figure 4-A exhibited that the recycling

process declined the FN of AC mixture by 18.2 % while it declined by 66.6 % after healing. The PM increased by (100, and 340) % for recycled and after healing under DDPSS cycles respectively. Such behavior may be related to the increment in the flexibility of the mixture after

recycling. When the AC mixtures were subjected to microcracks healing process as exhibited in Figure 4-B, the PM declined significantly by (50, and 10) % for aged AC mixture after the start of the loading and at failure respectively. However, the recycled AC mixture shows no significant variation in PM after the start of loading while it exhibits decline in

the PM by 18.7 % at failure when compared with that of AC mixtures before healing. The FN declined by 44 % for recycled AC mixture after healing while the variation in FN was not significant for aged AC mixture among healings. Such behavior complies with the work reported by Miljković et al., [3]; and Sarsam, [6].

Fig. 4: Influence of healing and recycling on the FN at DPSS.

Influence of Testing Mode on the Behavior of AC Mixture

The influence of testing mode on the behavior of AC mixture is significant; DITS exhibits more PM in the AC mixtures than that of the DDPSS before and after the microcracks healing process. This could be related to the diametral loading of DITS which creates indirect tensile resistance to repeated tensile stresses, the aggregate particles have more chance to roll over each other and move in the horizontal direction as compared to the case of restricted movement of aggregate particles under double punching shear stresses. The FN of aged AC mixture before healing at DDPSS is lower by 58 % and its PM is lower by 87.5 % than that at DITS. However, after the healing process, the FN of aged AC mixture at DPSS is lower by 70 % and its PM is lower by 70

% than that at DITS. On the other hand, when the aged AC mixtures were recycled, the influence of testing mode on FN was not significant before and after the healing process.

Healing and Recycling Indices

The recycling and healing indices of RAP mixtures is a quantitative measure used to enhance the quality and evaluate the efficiency of rejuvenator material and its ability to self-repair the initiated microcracks and recover its mechanical properties after sustaining damage. It is typically expressed as a ratio or percentage of the material property after recycling or a healing period to its original property of the control RAP. It was determined for the various AC mixtures based on the mathematical equations (1, and 2) and presented in Table 4.

$$\text{Recycling index (\%)} = [\text{FN after recycling} / \text{FN before recycling}] \times 100 \% \text{ -----(1)}$$

Healing index (%) = [FN after healing / FN before healing] x 100% -----(2)

Table 4: Recycling and Healing indices.

Type of AC pavement layer	Indices at DITS	Indices at DDPSS
Recycling index (%) before healing (at failure)	30	60
Recycling index (%) after healing (at failure)	10	33.3
Healing index (at failure)	66.6	66.6

It can be observed that the recycling index before healing is lower by 50 % for DITS test as compared with that at DDPSS test. However, the recycling index after healing is lower by 30 % for DITS test as compared with that at DDPSS test. On the other hand, the healing index at failure showed no significant variation among the testing mode.

CONCLUSIONS

The limitations of materials as well as the testing program may address following conclusions:

- FN declined by 212 % after recycling and declined by 44.4 % after healing when tested by DITS.
- PM increased by 14.2 after recycling while it declined by 166 % at failure for both aged and recycled mixtures after healing when tested by DITS.
- FN of AC mixture declined by 18.2 % and declined by 66.6 % after healing under DDPSS cycles.
- PM increased by (100, and 340) % for recycled and after healing under DDPSS cycles respectively.
- The recycling index before healing is lower by 50 % for DITS test as compared with that at DDPSS test. 6- The recycling index after healing is lower by 30 % for DITS test as compared with that at DDPSS test. 7- The healing index at failure showed no significant variation among the testing mode.
- 8- FN is recommended as a sound measure for the efficiency of recycling process.

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